

Assessment of Neighborhood Association for Shelter Assistance Implementation in Davao Oriental: Basis for Program Enhancement

A Thesis Submitted to the Professional Schools of the
University of Mindanao, Davao City

In Partial Fulfilment of the Requirements for the Degree of
Master in Social Work Major in Direct Practice

Ronald Gomez Ulgasan
Minda B. Brigoli, Drd (Co-Author)

May, 2022

APPROVAL SHEET

This thesis entitled, **ASSESSMENT OF NEIGHBORHOOD ASSOCIATION FOR SHELTER ASSISTANCE IMPLEMENTATION IN DAVAO ORIENTAL: BASIS FOR PROGRAM ENHANCEMENT** prepared and submitted by **RONALD GOMEZ ULGASAN** in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of Master in Social Work Major in Direct Practice, has been examined and is hereby recommended for approval and acceptance.

MINDA B. BRIGOLI, DRD
Adviser

PANEL OF EXAMINERS

APPROVED by the Panel of Examiners on Oral Examination with a grade of

JOEL B. TAN, CPA, DBA
Chairperson

EUFEMIA L. ROBLES, DSD
Member

GIRLIE E. AMARILLO, DSD
Member

DR. IZREIL ZERIAH KANDA
Member

ACCEPTED in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of Master in Social Work Major in Direct Practice.

Comprehensive Examination: **PASSED**

EUGENIO S. GUHAO, JR., DM
Chief Academic Officer

DEDICATION

I dedicate my master's thesis to my Mama and Papa who have always been a source of inspiration, and encouragement throughout my pursuit for education.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

My journey for a Diploma in Social Work at the University of the Philippines started in the year 2013 to 2017, and I will pursue my Master in Social Work at the University of Mindanao in the year 2018 to 2023. After 10 years of hard work and perseverance, I completed my Diploma/Master in Social Work.

I would like to acknowledge and give my warmest thanks to my thesis adviser, Dr. Minda B. Brigoli, who made this work possible. Her guidance and advice carried me through all the stages of thesis writing.

I would also like to give thanks to Dr. Rinante Genuba, thesis statistician for his expertise in statistical data.

I would also like to thank my panel members Dr. Joel B. Tan; Dr. Izreil Zeria Kanda, Dr. Girlie E. Amarillo and Dr. Eufemia L. Robles for making my final defense a successful one, and for your brilliant comments and suggestions, thanks to you.

I would like to give special thanks to Mr. Miguel H. Panugan Jr.

I would like to thank my family and friends for their love and support.

I would also like to extend my thanks to Ma'am Ma. Lourdes S. Rafanan, RSW, MSSW for the words of encouragement and support with her presence during the distribution of questionnaire and family food packs in every NASA communities.

I would also like to thank Mr. Aljon A. Egos for helping me in data tabulation and during public forums, and final oral defense, your skills in computers is highly appreciated.

I would also like to thank my colleagues in the government service of the Provincial Social Welfare and Development Office.

Finally, I would like to thank our Almighty Father, for letting me through all the difficulties. I have experienced your guidance day by day.

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to evaluate the Neighborhood Association for Shelter Assistance (NASA) Implementation in Davao Oriental and to create a Program Enhancement based on the findings of the study. Also, to compare the respondents' assessment when grouped by their profile. This employed the quantitative descriptive-comparative research design. Using a stratified random sampling with the proportional allocation, a total of 184 respondents out of the total NASA population from nine sites in District 2 of the Province of Davao Oriental were surveyed using a researcher-made, standardized questionnaire. By employing frequency count, weighted mean, and ANOVA as statistical tools, descriptive and inferential statistics were analyzed. Results revealed that the profile of beneficiary-respondents varies in terms of age, sex, marital status, educational attainment, monthly income, occupation, number of household members and number of years as beneficiary. Further, the perceived level of program implementation of the NASA in terms of disaster resilience, participation and project management, timeliness, accessibility, and sustainability are very high; hence the implementation of the project has been efficient and effective. Nonetheless, it has to be improved to adapt to the demands and hazards of today's socio-economic standards of living. Meanwhile, the significance of the difference in the perceived level of program implementation of NASA when analyzed by beneficiary-respondent's profile were found out that all of the indicators except the educational attainment revealed no significant difference; hence regardless of their differences in their demographic profile, majority of them have similar responses. Finally, despite the high level of manifestation of the success indicators implementation of NASA based on disaster resilience, participation and project management, timeliness, accessibility, and sustainability; it is conclusive that there is a need of intervention by the LGU and other stakeholders for the project in order to enhance and improve its serviceability in the aforementioned factors.

Keywords:- Discipline, Topic, Research Design, Inferential Statistical Tool, NASA Davao Oriental Enhancement Program, Philippines.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Title Page	1788
Approval Sheet	1789
Dedication	1790
Acknowledgement	1791
Abstract	1792
Table of Contents	1793
List of Tables	1795
List of Figures	1796
Chapter 1 Introduction	1797
Rationale	1797
Definition of Terms	1799
Conceptual Framework	1799
Research Gap	1799
Research Objectives	1800
Null Hypothesis	1800
Significance of the Study	1800
Chapter 2 Method	1801
Research Respondent	1801
Materials and Instrument	1801
Design and Procedures	1802
Statistical Tools	1802
Ethical Consideration	1802
Chapter 3 Results and Discussion	1805
Chapter 4 Conclusion and Recommendation	1812
References	1813

APPENDICES

Level of Program Implementation of NASA in terms of Disaster Resilience1814
Level of Program Implementation of NASA in terms of Participation and Mgt.....1814
Level of Program Implementation of NASA in terms of Timeliness1814

Level of Program Implementation of NASA in terms of Accessibility1814
Level of Program Implementation of NASA in terms of Disaster Sustainability.....1815
Survey Questionnaire1815

LIST OF TABLES

Table	Page no.
Table 1 Respondents Age, Sex, Marital Status, Educational Attainment and Monthly Income	1805
Table 2 Respondents Occupation, Household Members, Years as Beneficiary	1806
Table 3 Level of Program Implementation of NASA	1807
Table 4 Statistical Difference on Perceived Level of Program Implementation by Age	1808
Table 5 Statistical Difference on Perceived Level of Program Implementation by Sex	1808
Table 6 Statistical Difference on Perceived Level of Program Implementation by Marital Status	1808
Table 7 Statistical Difference on Perceived Level of Program Implementation by Educational Attainment	1809
Table 8 Statistical Difference on Perceived Level of Program Implementation by Monthly Income	1809
Table 9 Statistical Difference on Perceived Level of Program Implementation by Occupation	1809
Table 10 Statistical Difference on Perceived Level of Program Implementation by Household	1810
Table 11 Statistical Difference on Perceived Level of Program Implementation by Years as Beneficiary	1810

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1 The Conceptual Paradigm of the Study	1799
---	------

CHAPTER ONE INTRODUCTION

A. *Rationale*

Learning from the past can help us respond more effectively in the future in a world where the demand for humanitarian shelter far outpaces agency capacity and funding to support individuals in need of assistance (Global Shelter Cluster, 2019). There is a requirement and obligation to involve and enhance local capacities in every shelter response in order to enable lasting solutions due to cities increasing at an unprecedented rate and the demand for adequate, affordable housing for their citizens, which remains an issue globally (Oudshoorn et al., 2018). Considering that only 13% of global cities offer affordable housing, it is clear that cities are becoming cognizant of the need for action (UN Habitat, 2016).

The Federal Emergency Management Agency of the United States of America noted in a publication that following disasters, communities frequently face challenges requiring innovative options for both short-term and long-term housing for communities confronting varied geographical, infrastructure, and socioeconomic issues. Long-term recovery depends on successfully relocating survivors into post-disaster housing (FEMA, 2020).

Despite the imminent threat of earthquakes in that region, the Los Angeles Housing Department found in a survey conducted in 2012 that most government and nonprofit groups in Southern California lacked catastrophe housing plans. Recently, after-action reports on disasters including hurricanes, wildfires, and flooding have continued to bring attention to unresolved problems with providing efficient and effective housing solutions for disaster survivors (LACP, 2012).

The Australian Ministries of Housing, Planning, and Local Government envision a coordinated approach to address current and upcoming housing affordability concerns. The framework includes the specific task of developing a national framework for affordable housing appraisal (Fagan, Gurrin, Milligan & Phibbs, 2007). Also, the World Economic Forum (2019) published an Insight Report that analyzes the dynamics of housing from both the supply and demand sides. On the supply side, these expenses include those for design and development, improvements to property tenure, financial models, and land acquisition and regulation. On the demand side, difficulties include determining who is eligible for cheap housing, the variety of tenure patterns for different demographics, and providing sufficient financial access.

Habitat 111 in Quito, Ecuador, endorsed the New Urban Agenda in 2016, and by 2030, states are urged to advance "national, subnational, and municipal housing policies that assist the progressive fulfillment of the right to sufficient housing for everyone." Yet, housing costs are increasing at a rate that is out of step with household incomes, which is problematic for lower-income households in areas with a dearth of social or public housing.

In San Francisco, the lowest 5% of earnings make around \$650 per month, while the lowest 5% of renters pay about \$1,500 per month (Fidler & Sabir, 2019). 330 million urban residents, according to McKinsey, either resided in substandard housing or were experiencing financial difficulty as a result of housing prices (McKinsey Global Institute, 2014). 1.6 billion households, or 1.6 billion people, are predicted to exist by 2025, and 2.5 billion by 2050. In addition, over 50% of people in Africa live in informal settlements, compared to less than a quarter of the population in China and India (Florida, 2017).

In the Philippines, a report entitled Rapid Assessment of the Performance of Post-Disaster Housing Reconstruction Approaches Submitted to the World Bank-Philippine Office provides a quick assessment of the Department of Social Welfare and Development's (DSWD's) Core/Modified Shelter Assistance Program (CSAP/MSAP) and the National Housing Authority's (NHA's) and Social Housing and Finance Corporation's (SHF's) post-disaster reconstruction initiatives (SHFC). Six criteria were quickly evaluated for these three housing options: disaster resilience, participation of families affected by disasters, speed, accessibility, and sustainability. Notwithstanding this, the Philippines continues to have challenges in meeting the needs of the urban poor who are homeless. The Urban Development and Housing Act made a commitment to address the socialized housing demand brought on by the growing urbanization. The implementation of housing policy by the public and private sectors, notably in Davao City, to assure compliance and the mechanisms. In order to speed up the production of socialized housing through a balanced housing development program, the municipal government of Davao must confront the issue of rising urban homelessness with inventiveness and urgency (Angel, Majid & Pampanga, 2015).

Making government housing efforts accessible and cheap for the poor will become a major issue in the near future. Urban shantytowns and unofficial settlements have an obvious increase in housing needs. The government's obligation to make it easier to access housing options and services needs to be made clearer. The government's attempts to solve the housing situation during the past 40 years have fallen short of tackling the fundamental issues with housing, especially for the poor (Philippines Development Plan, 2017).

The report is based on a visit by the Philippine Working Group to the three relocation sites in Cagayan De Oro (CDO) that were established following Tropical Storm Sendong and where the three housing plans were put into place. Three additional sites

were included after the study's focus was shifted to the DSWD's CSAP/MSAP. These locations are located in the Davao Oriental towns of Boston and Tarragona, where MSAP housing survived Typhoon Pablo in 2012.

Additionally, local government units in the Philippines offer assistance with problems related to housing shelter for disaster victims and poor families, including but not limited to land and project site development, technical manpower such as foremen, construction equipment/tools, food for work, and others. Additionally, this entails organizing residents into a Neighborhood Association for Shelter Help and increasing their capacity (UN, 2017).

The Neighborhood Association for Shelter Assistance (NASA), a group made up of those who will benefit from this housing project, supports teamwork in achieving the project's objectives. As a matter of fact, the organization addresses the community's weaknesses and gives it the tools it needs to make the main housing livable and sustainable (DSWD, 2011). DSWD has highlighted that the Bayanihan family has many strong supporters in the neighborhood. They also serve as the meeting's chairpersons as the families go through meetings for social preparation, election of officers, and committee formation. In the end, if the recipients are punished for failing to show up for meetings, declining to join Bayanihan, arriving late, or even drinking alcohol, they have violated the law. The Neighborhood Organization for Shelter Help receives the fine, which is placed into its account, and uses the funds for its annual budget (Mamuyac, 2014).

The Bayanihan family is well-supported in the community, according to DSWD, who has highlighted this. The families have meetings to plan social events, elect officers, and organize committees, and they also act as the meeting's chairs during these times. Ultimately, if the receivers are penalized for missing meetings, declining to join Bayanihan, showing up late, or even drinking alcohol, they have broken the law. The Neighborhood Association for Shelter Assistance receives the fine and deposits it into its account. The organization then uses the money for its annual budget (Mamuyac, 2014).

The Neighborhood Association for Shelter Assistance (NASA) was created and locally launched by the Provincial Government through the Provincial Social Welfare and Development Office in Davao Oriental as an appropriate reaction to the province's 80% of disaster-prone districts. It is a resettlement program that offers housing aid to displaced squatter families and homeless disaster victims with little money to rebuild their homes. In order to teach in the beneficiaries of the eventual NASA the value of social responsibility in preserving and supporting the aforementioned shelter provision project, the local government made a Memorandum of Agreement with them. According to the guiding principles of the National Incident Management System, the majority of events start and terminate locally and often demand a coordinated effort by regional organizations, the commercial sector, and NGOs. The Neighborhood Association for Shelter Assistance (NASA), an association of the main shelter beneficiaries, was created to support collective action in achieving the project's objectives, according to a separate publication by the Environmental Science for Social Change (ESSC, 2014). While enabling recipients to make the main shelter livable and more sustainable, the association also addresses the community's vulnerabilities. To boost value creation in social housing, however, there is a need for project evaluation to be done carefully. The review procedure could be hampered by the project's diversity, dynamics, and unclear objectives. The evaluation of social housing projects is primarily concerned with product features without clearly establishing a connection to anticipated goals. The methodology for the evaluation of social housing projects is based on a hierarchical model for value generation that ties attributes to outcomes and desired aims. This approach was taken into consideration and can be used to compare projects from various housing initiatives. The primary contributions of the study are the establishment of techniques and uses as conceptual models for describing value generation and that can describe the components of housing projects, the effects of use, and project objectives (Bonatto, Formosa & Miron, 2011).

Similar to this, the research study conducted by Amole and Ibem (2010) developed and tested a theoretical and conceptual framework for an alternative approach to the evaluation of public housing programs in Nigeria, and it aims to address limitations of current approaches where one theory or discipline is used to evaluate public housing programs.

Woodruff and Gardial (1996) proposed a hierarchical model that is divided into three levels: (a) attributes: this level is more concrete and refers to the physical characteristics, resources, or components of a product; (b) consequences of use: refers to positive or negative experiences that result from the use of the product; such consequences are usually mentioned (1982). This model was created to make it clear how customers classify product information in their memories and to help us comprehend the actions that influence a consumer's choice to buy (Gutman, 1982). Woodruff and Gardial (1996) expanded the applicability of the means-end model to take into consideration both the value produced while using the product and the value wanted at the time of purchase. These theories served as the basis for this study, which looked at the Neighborhood Association for Shelter Assistance (NASA) from the perspectives of its members as it created a program for reform.

B. Definition of Terms

In this research to have a common understanding of terms used by the researcher, operational definitions are provided for the terms below.

➤ *Evaluation/Assessment*

This refers to the reliable and objective valuation of a continuing or completed program or project, its policy implementation, and outcomes. The objective is to decide the significance and completion of goals, effectiveness, impact and sustainability.

➤ *Program Enhancement*

This refers to the doing of intrusiveness with the outcome, particularly of a condition as to improve functioning.

➤ *Neighborhood Association for Shelter Assistance (NASA)*

This refers to a group of beneficiaries organized with the assistance of the Local Government Unit for the purpose of availing housing programs or projects. In the context of the study, this will be association to be evaluated as perceived by the beneficiaries to become the basis of intervention. These beneficiaries are victims of natural and manmade disasters or those affected by development-induced situations.

C. Conceptual Framework

Fig 1 The Conceptual Paradigm of the Study

The conceptual paradigm of the study is shown in Figure 1. It presents the socio-demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, marital status, educational attainment, monthly income, occupation, number of household members, and years as beneficiary as being influenced by the level of assessment to the Neighborhood Association for Shelter Assistance (NASA) program as indicated by disaster resilience, participation, and project management, timeliness, accessibility, and sustainability. All of them will serve as the determining factors for the anticipated outcome as the foundation for an intervention based on the study's findings.

D. Research Gap

Although several research works have been done to monitor and evaluate housing projects and the status of the organizations with immediate concerns on shelter programs, projects, and activities, no such research has been made to evaluate the Neighborhood Association for Shelter Assistance (NASA) more particularly in the locality. Accordingly, there is a dearth of information on the status of the shelter project outcomes. Thus, the researcher is prompted to pursue this study. Further, the absence of a research study in the national and the local setting has motivated the researcher to conduct this investigation. Through this study, the findings could become a basis in crafting programs and interventions that will help NASA based on the findings of the research evaluation. As such, distinct management and sustainability of the project will be evident.

E. *Research Objectives*

This research study generally aims to conduct a comparative-evaluative study on the implementation of the Neighborhood Association for Shelter Assistance (NASA) as a basis for enhancement program. Specifically, it aims:

➤ *To Describe the Profile of Beneficiary-Respondents in Terms of:*

- Age
- Sex
- Marital Status
- Educational Attainment
- Monthly Income
- Occupation
- Number of Household Members
- Number of Years as Beneficiary

➤ *To Measure the Perceived Level of Program Implementation of the NASA in Terms of:*

- Disaster Resilience
- Participation and Project Management
- Timeliness
- Accessibility
- Sustainability

➤ *To Determine the Significance of the Difference in the Perceived Level of Program Implementation of NASA when Analyzed by Beneficiary-Respondent's Profile.*

➤ *To Propose an Intervention Based on the Results of the Study.*

F. *Null Hypothesis*

Based on the above-mentioned objectives, this study tests the following null hypothesis:

➤ *There are no significant differences in the perceived level of program implementation of NASA when analyzed by beneficiary-respondent's profile.*

G. *Significance of the Study*

It is hoped that the results of this study will disclose relevant information regarding the implementation of the Neighborhood Association for Shelter Assistance (NASA) leading to propose intervention program and to the global concern of shelter assistance assessment need. At any rate, the research outcomes will be contributory to the:

The output of this research study will provide relevant data regarding the evaluation of the current and previous shelter project outcomes of NASA as the basis for intervention. This will help increase community capacity building and guidelines implementation by the members of the association themselves.

This will serve as the reference of the Provincial Social Welfare and Development Office to ascertain the significance of the comparison of the NASA program based on the assessment conducted in order for them to look for relevant ways and means to deal with the matter at hand as the government agency directly in-charge of the association.

This will be an avenue for the local government units from the barangay, city or municipality, and the provide to identify the status of the program gearing towards crafting programs, projects, and activities to uplift the level of progress and development of the association.

This will be a venue for reference for researchers. The results of this study could also help future researchers to come up with information that would be a basis for further studies. This study will add to the scholarly research and the body of knowledge and literature, particularly in dealing with the evaluation of shelter associations like NASA.

CHAPTER TWO METHOD

This chapter presents the research respondent, materials and instruments, design and procedures, statistical tools, and ethical considerations.

A. *Research Respondent*

The study was conducted within the nine (9) Neighborhood Association for Shelter Assistance (NASA) of the District II of the Province of Davao Oriental wherein they are the respondents. In the selection of the respondents, this research utilized one of the most common forms of probability sampling which is stratified random sampling with the proportional allocation (Parsons, 2017),

Sampling was done until a specific number of units for various strata have been selected. Using the formula in getting the proportionate numbers of respondents, the subjects of this study were identified from the total population of the nine (9) NASA sub-divided accordingly by the site.

The researcher identified a total of 184 respondents out of the total 296 NASA population who were surveyed in this research endeavor using stratified random sampling with the proportional allocation (Parsons, 2017). These randomly selected respondents were treated with utmost ethical considerations. Further, selection process included all the incumbent and previous officers of the NASA and all its existing official members regardless of gender and age.

Additionally, these respondents were coming from different sites with varied settings as there were sites from rural areas and urban places. Nevertheless, the distribution of these respondents was based on the total population of the NASA they belong taken proportionately.

However, non-members or inactive members who are dwelling in the sites of NASA are excluded and do not qualify as respondents of the study. Inactive members are those who do not attend regular meetings and do not assume the duties and responsibilities of being such. Further, the respondents may withdraw their consent at any time and discontinue their participation without penalty. Their responses were voluntary. Their refusal respond would involve no loss of benefits to which they were otherwise entitled. They were not waiving any legal claims, rights of remedies because of their responses in this research study.

The study was conducted on the beneficiaries of the LGU Shelter Assistance Project organized into the Neighborhood Association for Shelter Assistance in Davao Oriental. More specifically in district II of the said province.

Davao Oriental is located in the southeast of Davao Region and is bordered by the Celebes Sea and Davao Gulf in the south, Agusan del Sur and Surigao del Sur in the north, Davao de Oro in the west, and the Pacific Ocean in the east. It is regarded as the easternmost region of the nation, with Pusan Point serving as its easternmost landmark. The province consists of one (1) city, ten (10) municipalities with 183 barangays, and is divided into two (2) legislative districts.

With a land size of 5,679.64 sq. km., or 32.82 percent of the total regional land area, Davao Oriental is the largest province in the Davao Region. About 2,009.44 sq. km., or 3155.02 sq. miles, or 35 percent of the area, is designated as alienable and disposable, and 55.55 sq. kilometers are designated as forests.

There is a distinct rainy season in Davao Oriental and a brief dry season, with the heaviest rain falling from November to January, especially in coastal areas. The province occasionally encounters crises and natural disasters that resulted in the destruction and decay of certain inadequate shelters. This study is pertinent to the area since it will assess the shelter support provided to local beneficiaries who are suffering from calamities and disasters.

B. *Materials And Instrument*

A researcher-made questionnaire was the tool used in obtaining information on the demographic profile of the respondents and the extent of the shelter project outcomes in terms of disaster resilience, participation and project management, timeliness, accessibility, and sustainability along with their demographic profile. Each context had a total of five (5) predictor statements except for participation and project management which has ten (10) statements.

The scale of the questionnaire of this research study which pertains to the following indicators in the context of disaster resilience, participation and project management, timeliness, accessibility, and sustainability are as follow:

For a scale of 5 this means that the measure of the variable is always true; 4 means that the measure of the variable is often true; 3 means that the measure of the variable is sometimes true; 2 means that the measure of the variable is seldom true; and 1 means that the measure of the variable is almost never true respectively.

The questionnaire utilized the Likert scale with descriptive equivalent and interpretation to measure the level of manifestation of the predictor statements. By asking respondents to rate their agreement with a series of statements about a subject, Likert (1932) created the idea of evaluating attitudes by drawing on both the cognitive and affective aspects of attitudes.

Before using the researcher-made questionnaire, it was presented first to the panel of examinees before to the group of experts for validation. The comments of experts were properly taken and incorporated for finalization. The combined scores of the five expert validators generated an average of 4.8 for clarity of direction and items; 4.4 for presentation and organization of items; 4.2 for suitability of items; 4.4 for adequateness of items per category or indicator; 4.8 for attainment of purpose; 4.4 for objectivity; and 4.2 for scale and evaluation rating scale. This means that the research questionnaire has an average score of 4.46 which further indicates that it is very good.

A pilot test of the survey questionnaire was done in the NASA site of District I in the Province of Davao Oriental with 30 respondents. They were made to answer the researcher-made questionnaires. All response were tallied and subjected to computation using Cronbach alpha to gauge the reliability of the questionnaire. Also, the pilot testing produced reliability data for Cronbach's Alpha of .860 and Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items of .855. This indicates that there is good internal consistency.

C. Design and Procedures

The quantitative-comparative research design was applied in this study by the researcher. et. Tourigny Al. (2011) proposes this approach on purpose to identify the relationships between the variables. Belli (2008) further argues that it is important to take all plausible explanations into account when analyzing the variables and drawing conclusions without being able to make firm declarations. In order to make the subject easier to understand, use published studies.

Moreover, a questionnaire was used as the study tool. The questionnaire that was given to respondents and used as the main instrument constituted the basis for the data collection. To facilitate quick access to the tabulation of the data, the researcher utilized *Google Forms* in the encoding, distribution, administration, and access of the questionnaire. The questionnaire was created to gather sufficient data related to the study's goals.

This was pertinent to the current study since it addressed the comparative assessment and evaluation of housing projects as a foundation for the intervention of the LGU Shelter Assistance Project structured into Neighborhood Association for Shelter Assistance (NASA).

➤ *In the Conduct of the Study, the Following Processes were Employed:*

- The researcher asked permission from the elected officials of the barangay. Then, to the Neighborhood Association for Shelter Assistance officials wherein the respondents are in the community. Upon the approval of the request letter, a formal communication was distributed to the members of the Neighborhood Association for Shelter Assistance to oversee the questionnaire of the research study conducted.
- After the approval and arrangement of the schedule, the researcher attended the scheduled monthly meeting of the Neighborhood Association for Shelter Assistance beneficiaries and shall distribute the questionnaire to the target respondents. The results of the study were collected, tabulated, and computed utilizing scales and statistical analysis. Then the findings were analyzed and interpreted based on the gathered data. On the basis of the study's findings, the researcher then offered conclusions and suggestions.

D. Statistical Tools

Guided by a statistician a descriptive survey design method of analysis from varied standpoints of the respondents was developed to show the results. Specifically, the following statistical tools were utilized with the help of a statistician.

- **Frequency Count.** This was used to describe the survey respondents' profile.
- **Weighted Mean.** This was used to characterize how the respondents regarded the implementation of the NASA program.
- **T-test and/or ANOVA.** When the beneficiary-respondent analyzes the perceived level of program execution, this will establish the importance of the discrepancy.
- **Multivariate Analysis of Variance (MANOVA).** The extent of the Neighborhood Association for Shelter Assistance in terms of disaster resilience, involvement and project management, timeliness, accessibility, and sustainability was compared to the socio-demographic profile of the respondents to identify any noteworthy discrepancies. The level of significance for alpha is set at 0.05 for testing the null hypothesis. This will deal with the outcomes of objective 3.

E. Ethical Consideration

To assure that this research follows the necessary rules in conducting research and that no rights of any participants or data collected may have offended somebody, this study passed the review by University of Mindanao Ethics Review Committee (UMERC) with Certification Number U MERC-2022-109 which guaranteed that in the conduct of this study. The researcher

followed all guidelines in carrying out the protocol evaluations and standardized criteria, especially in handling the population and data, including but not limited to:

➤ *Voluntary Participation*

The choice to participate was entirely up to each and every NASA member-respondent who took part in the study, with no restrictions or penalties. For the sake of the study, the researcher made sure no special social groups would be singled out. The study's respondents had no known vulnerabilities. The beneficiaries were all in the capacity to decide whether to participate or not, as they were identified as respondents of the research.

The only criterion used to select the subjects for this study was how pertinent they were to the practice problem under investigation. Out of the entire NASA population polled for this research project, 184 responders were selected by the researcher. All of the NASA's current and former officers, as well as all of its current official members, regardless of gender or age, participated in the selection process. These respondents also came from various locations with a variety of situations, including both urban and rural areas. However, the distribution of these respondents was according to their proportionate share of the entire population of the NASA. Non-members or inactive members who reside on NASA property are not included in the study's sample and are not considered responders. Inactive members are people who hold their membership obligations but do not regularly attend meetings. Also, the respondents are free to stop participating and withdraw their consent at any moment without facing any consequences. They gave voluntary answers. They wouldn't lose any of the benefits to which they were normally entitled if they didn't react. Because of their responses to this research study, they were not waiving any claims, rights, or recourse in the legal sense.

The rights of the respondents to participate in the study will therefore be carefully regarded and respected when the goal and advantages of the study have been explained to the respondent.

➤ *Privacy and Confidentiality*

The study adhered to strict confidentiality standards and kept the respondent's personal and/or professional information that might be needed in private. The responders' records were not publicly available. The researcher made sure that all data remained private. To preserve the respondents' confidentiality and protect their identity, specific names were replaced with codes. The researcher's own possessions were used to preserve and protect hard copies of the data (with codes only). Every piece of information that needed to remain private was handled with the utmost care. Paper records should be disposed of or destroyed in a way that prevents information from being reconstructed. Burning, shredding then cross-shredding, pulping, and crushing are acceptable procedures for getting rid of paper records. It was confirmed that the researcher consistently followed and adhered with the 2012 Data Privacy Act's standards.

➤ *Informed Consent Process*

The study's respondents will have no trouble understanding the researcher's questionnaire because it is free of technical jargon. It gives the general public a comprehensive understanding of the advantages the organization generated as a result of the study's conduct. The administration of the Province of Davao Oriental, including the province's Local Government Units and the affected community, gave its approval and support to the administration of the questionnaire. Also, the in-charge staff members of the Provincial Social Welfare and Development Office (PSWDO) provided their consent and approval. As a result, no respondent was ever handed a research questionnaire without first getting approval from the proper command channels.

➤ *Recruitment*

The respondents of this study were limited only to the members of the NASA in District 11 of Davao Oriental regardless of age and gender. The researcher identified a total of 184 respondents out of the total NASA population. The researcher asked permission from the elected officials of the barangay. Then, to the Neighborhood Association for Shelter Assistance officials wherein the respondents are in the community. Upon the approval of the request letter, a formal communication was distributed to the members of the Neighborhood Association for Shelter Assistance to oversee the questionnaire of the research study conducted.

After the approval and arrangement of the schedule, the researcher attended the scheduled monthly meeting of the Neighborhood Association for Shelter Assistance beneficiaries and shall distribute the questionnaire to the target respondents.

➤ *Risks*

During the conduct of this study, no high risk was expected in the setting. The researcher followed the protocol as set by the Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF) that all respondents were properly taken care of and were free from harm. However, some risks were discussed because of some incidents that may happen anytime especially in our situation now with the COVID-19 pandemic. Risks were avoided to the point that the researcher ensured that survey questionnaires were answered by the participants through strict measures of health protocols. Further, the respondents underwent briefing and debriefing from the resident social worker before and after the conduct of the study.

➤ *Benefits*

The study may be useful to the entire NASA. The researcher allotted 14 days duration in the acceptance of the responses. Answering the survey cannot affect their daily work or they can answer the survey form during their break time. The benefit of the respondents was evident as they will be the primary beneficiaries of the intervention. Moreover, each of the respondents received family food packs from the researcher as a token of appreciation.

➤ *Plagiarism*

No representation that could have led to plagiarism was used in the study. Grammar consistency and the reduction of similarity index will be ensured by the use of Grammarly, Turnitin software, and/or any other plagiarism checker, enabling the researcher the freedom to convey the idea in her own words while still drawing on the work of the authors of other studies.

➤ *Fabrication*

The study was founded on a number of credible and accurate studies. It makes sure that the researcher does not extrapolate a story from the author's writing and instead states the author's notion based on her own comprehension and ideas. The writers of the manuscript correctly anchored and acknowledged the manuscript; there was no fabrication of data, outcomes, or even intentionally putting towards conclusions.

➤ *Falsification*

In order to make the study fit, it did not overstate the data or excessively credit prior works. The theoretical foundation and models will be drawn from trustworthy and accurate sources.

➤ *Conflict of Interest*

There was no conflict of interest-related evidence in this study. The study had no bearing on any side interests. It only focuses on issues of primary importance, such as the wellbeing of the respondents and the reliability of research trends. To avoid potential conflicts of interest, the researcher made sure there was no personal bias in their acquaintance with NASA personnel.

➤ *Deceit*

Transparency was maintained throughout the survey's execution thanks to the study. First, because of the organization, authority, and credibility to carry out this investigation. By way of a letter requesting authorization and a personal conversation outlining the purpose of the study, the researcher requested approval from the Provincial Social Welfare and Development Office of Davao Oriental. The Local Government Units of the City and Municipalities in District 11 underwent the same process. This study already followed the guidelines of transparency by clearly disclosing to the respondents that they were polled using questionnaires. The responders were also made aware of the goal of the study. Also, transcripts of documents and interview notes were shown to the respondents for validation and approval. Moreover, the participants could contact the study's researcher at any moment to learn more about the study's findings.

➤ *Permission from Institution/Location*

For the purpose of obtaining authorization to search for and collect data inside a particular institution and place, the study used a formal letter addressed to the authorized employees. The barangay's elected officials granted permission after the researcher requested it. Officials of the Neighborhood Association for Shelter Help in the neighborhood where the respondents reside. The meeting was conducted inside the premises by the researcher in a religious manner.

➤ *Technology Issues*

The researcher used Google Forms to encode, distribute, administer, and retrieve the questionnaire so that the data tabulation could be accessed quickly.

➤ *Authorship*

For this study, the researcher showed commitment, dedication, dependability, and credibility. Yet because he was a novice researcher using this technique, he had to examine pertinent articles and publications on quantitative research design. To further confirm the authenticity and reliability of the data acquired, the researcher routinely consulted with his thesis mentor and other professionals in the field. Due to this, the advisor was in a position to greatly aid in improving the study. The advisor had a good amount of credibility, ingenuity, and creativity. Also, the knowledgeable panelists enhanced this study's investigation.

CHAPTER THREE RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the data analyses, interpretation, and discussion in answer to the problems identified in this research study.

A. Profile of the Respondents According to Age, Sex, Marital Status, Educational Attainment, Monthly Income, Occupation, Number of Household Members, and Number of Years as Beneficiary

Table 1 is the profile of the respondents according to age, sex, marital status, educational attainment, monthly income.

From the table that majority of the respondents are ages 61 to 70 years old at 28.8% followed by 51-60 years old at 28.3%, 41-50 years old at 17.9%, 71 years old and above at 16.8%, 31-40 years old at 6.5%, and 30 years old and below at 1.6% as the lowest. For the sex, most respondents comprise males at 62% while females at 38%. As to their marital status, the majority are married at 66.8%, followed by widow/widower at 21.2%, live-in at 6.5%, and the lowest are single and separated at 2.7%. Based on their educational attainment, the majority of them are elementary level at 27.2%, followed by high school level at 22.3%, high school graduate at 21.2%, elementary graduate at 16.8, college level at 9.8, and college graduate are the lowest at 2.7%. Considering their monthly income, most of them are with 5,000 and below income at 65.2%, distantly followed by 5,000-10,000 at 29.3%, 10,001-15,000 at 3.3%, 20,001-25,000 at 1.6, and 15,001-20,000 at 0.5% as the lowest since there is no response in 25,000 and above income.

Table 1 Respondents Age, Sex, Marital Status, Educational Attainment, and Monthly Income

Categories	F	%
Age		
30 years old and below	3	1.6
31 – 40 years old	12	6.5
41 – 50 years old	33	17.9
51 – 60 years old	52	28.3
61 – 70 years old	53	28.8
71 years old and above	31	16.8
Sex		
Male	114	62
Female	70	38
Marital Status		
Single	5	2.7
Married	123	66.8
Widow/Widower	39	21.2
Separated	5	2.7
Live-in	12	6.5
Educational Attainment		
Elementary Level	50	27.2
Elementary Graduate	31	16.8
High School Level	41	22.3
High School Graduate	39	21.2
College Level	18	9.8
College Graduate	5	2.7
Monthly Income		
5,000 below	120	65.2
5,000 – 10,000	54	29.3
10,001 – 15,000	6	3.3
15,001 – 20,000	1	0.5
20,001 – 25,000	3	1.6
25,000 above	0	0
Total	184	100

Table 2 presents the respondents' profile on occupation, the number of household members, and several years as beneficiaries.

For their occupation, most of them are farmers at 59.2%, followed by fishermen at 12%, carpenters at 10.3%, public/private employees at 5.4%, and others at varying small percentages. Most of the members of their household have 1-5 members at 64.13%, 6-10 members at 35.3%, and 11-15 members at 0.5% as the lowest. Notably, from the 184 respondents, 107 have

benefited NASA for 21 years and above at 58.2%, followed by 16-20 years at 28.8%, then distantly followed by 11-15 years, below five years, and 6-10 years at 4.9%, 4.3%, and 3.8% respectively.

Table 2 Respondents Occupation, Household Members, Years as Beneficiary

Categories	F	%
Occupation		
Fisherman	22	12
Farmer	109	59.2
Carpenter	19	10.3
Private/Public Employee	10	5.4
Others		
Self-employed	5	2.7
Driver	1	0.5
Laborer	2	1.1
Food Vendor	1	0.5
Housewife	5	2.7
Fish Vendor	2	1.1
Salesman	1	0.5
Online Seller	1	0.5
Laundry Woman	2	1.1
OFW	1	0.5
Massage Therapist	1	0.5
BNS	1	0.5
Minister	1	0.5
Household Members		
1 – 5	118	64.13
6 – 10	65	35.3
11 – 15	1	0.5
16 – 20	0	0
21 – 25	0	0
26 above	0	0
Years as Beneficiary		
Below 5 years	8	4.3
6 – 10 years	7	3.8
11 – 15 years	9	4.9
16 – 20 years	53	28.8
21 years and above	107	58.2
Total	184	100

The findings revealed that based on the profile of the respondents, the majority of them are aged 61 to 70 years old, primarily males, married, mostly elementary level, with 5,000 and below income, farmers, with 1-5 members in the household, and have been beneficiaries of NASA for 21 years and above. Based on these data, this further implies that the beneficiaries belong to the underprivileged sector of society. They struggle financially with meager incomes that cannot suffice for their family members. These results support the notion that NASA approaches the issue of rising urban homelessness with innovation and urgency to hasten the creation of socialized housing through a balanced housing development policy (Angel, Majid & Pampanga, 2015). This supports even more the contention that the government's function in facilitating access to housing possibilities and services has to be made clear. Throughout the past 40 years, the government's efforts to address the housing crisis have failed to resolve the fundamental problems with housing, particularly for the poor (Philippine Development Plan, 2017).

B. Level of Program Implementation of the NASA

Table 3 presents the respondents' perceived level of program implementation of NASA regarding disaster resilience, participation and project management, timeliness, accessibility, and sustainability. As presented, the overall mean is 4.01, which means that the program implementation of NASA is high.

The respondents rated the five indicators of program implementation, participation, and project management as the highest with a high level, at 4.06, followed by disaster resilience and sustainability, which were also manifested at a high level by the beneficiaries at 4.05 and 4.01, respectively. On the other hand, timeliness was rated as the lowest, at 3.94, next to accessibility, at 3.98, although also described at a high level by the NASA beneficiaries.

Table 3 Level of Program Implementation of the NASA

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Disaster Resilience	0.76	4.05	High
Participation and Project Management	0.73	4.06	High
Timeliness	0.77	3.94	High
Accessibility	0.69	3.98	High
Sustainability	0.73	4.01	High
Overall	0.66	4.01	High

From the table, it can be inferred that the respondents regarded NASA's program implementation as high in disaster resilience, involvement, project management, timeliness, accessibility, and sustainability.

In terms of the disaster of disaster resilience, all five items obtained a mean equivalent to a high level, which means that NASA has a positive regard for implementing the project for the housing to be capable and resilient of withstanding natural disasters. But, additional disaster studies on hurricanes, wildfires, and flooding continue to point out persistent inadequacies in providing housing options that are practical and efficient for disaster survivors (LACP, 2012).

Significantly, NASA has successfully motivated members for project management and involvement, as evidenced by the extremely high degree of manifestation of the members' participation in activities related to home construction. This is consistent with the Environmental Science for Social Change (ESSC, 2014) reports, which revealed that the primary beneficiaries of shelter are organized into the Neighborhood Association for Shelter Assistance (NASA), an organization of the primary beneficiaries of shelter that encourages group action to achieve the project's objectives. Although it is too early to inquire about changes in beneficiaries' lives, a sense of empowerment can be seen based on the respondents' behaviors.

Regarding timeliness, the results of high-level manifestation show that NASA responds quickly to implementing changes in site selection, planning, development, and housing design and building. Coordination is required between those in charge of organizing relocation and the LGUs hosting the relocated family.

In terms of accessibility, the results showed high manifestation, which strongly indicates that NASA had carefully constructed the project in an accessible place with careful consideration of the site and the fundamental necessities for the members to be comfortable. This further emphasizes that the supply of these essential services must be considered as part of the planning for relocating sizable populations to ensure the people's quality of life.

The study also showed a high-level expression of sustainability, which suggests that the families in NASA are organized to enhance living conditions during the relocation and that the officers and members of their organization have carried out their duties to maintain the project. These results support the idea that the beneficiaries of this housing project were grouped to form the Neighborhood Association for Shelter Assistance (NASA), which supports teamwork in achieving the project's objectives. The organization does address the community's vulnerabilities and gives them the tools they need to make the main housing habitable and sustainable (DSWD, 2011).

The specific results for each indicator can be seen in the Appendices Table 2.1 to Table 2.5.

C. Significance of the Difference in the Perceived Level of Program Implementation of NASA when Analyzed by Beneficiary-Respondent's Profile

The ANOVA was used to determine the significance of the difference in the perceived level of program implementation of NASA when assessed by respondents when grouped according to age.

As shown in Table 4, there is no significant difference in the perceived level of program implementation as assessed by the respondents when grouped according to age. Overall, the F-value is .397, while the p-value is .850. In disaster resilience, the F-value is .533, while the p-value is .751. Regarding participation and project management, the F-value is .892, while the p-value is .487. Whereas for the timeliness, the F-value is .300 while the p-value is .912. For accessibility, the F-value is .635, while the p-value is .673. Meanwhile, for sustainability, the F-value is .600 while the p-value is .700. All factors are higher than the 0.05 level of significance; thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that respondents had the same perceptions of the program implementation of NASA regardless of age.

Table 4 Statistical Difference on Perceived Level of Program Implementation by Age

AGE			
Factors	F	p-value	Remarks
Disaster Resilience	.533	.751	Not Significant
Participation and Project Management	.892	.487	Not Significant
Timeliness	.300	.912	Not Significant
Accessibility	.635	.673	Not Significant
Sustainability	.600	.700	Not Significant
Overall	.397	.850	Not Significant

Further, to determine the significance of the difference in the perceived level of program implementation of NASA when analyzed as assessed by respondents when grouped according to sex, the ANOVA was used.

Table 5 shows no significant difference in the perceived level of program implementation as assessed by the respondents when grouped according to sex. Overall, the F-value is .340, while the p-value is .561. In disaster resilience, the F-value is .240, while the p-value is .625. Regarding participation and project management, the F-value is .642, while the p-value is .424. Whereas for the timeliness, the F-value is 1.356 while the p-value is .246. For accessibility, the F-value is .295, while the p-value is .588.

Meanwhile, for sustainability, the F-value is .374, while the p-value is .542. All factors are higher than the 0.05 level of significance; thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means there is no significant difference in the program implementation of NASA as assessed by the respondents when grouped by sex.

Table 5 Statistical Difference on Perceived Level of Program Implementation by Sex

SEX			
Factors	F	p-value	Remarks
Disaster Resilience	.240	.625	Not Significant
Participation and Project Management	.642	.424	Not Significant
Timeliness	1.356	.246	Not Significant
Accessibility	.295	.588	Not Significant
Sustainability	.374	.542	Not Significant
Overall	.340	.561	Not Significant

Furthermore, the ANOVA was used to determine the significance of the difference in the perceived level of program implementation of NASA when assessed by respondents when grouped according to marital status.

Table 6 shows no significant difference in the perceived level of program implementation as assessed by the respondents when grouped according to marital status. Overall, the F-value is .943, while the p-value is .440. In disaster resilience, the F-value is .370, while the p-value is .830. Regarding participation and project management, the F-value is 1.184, while the p-value is .319. Whereas for the timeliness, the F-value is 1.335 while the p-value is .259. For accessibility, the F-value is 1.178, while the p-value is .322.

Meanwhile, for sustainability, the F-value is .668, while the p-value is .615. All factors are higher than the 0.05 level of significance; thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means there is no significant difference in the program implementation of NASA as assessed by the respondents when grouped by marital status.

Table 6 Statistical Difference on Perceived Level of Program Implementation by Marital Status

MARITAL STATUS			
Factors	F	p-value	Remarks
Disaster Resilience	.370	.830	Not Significant
Participation and Project Management	1.184	.319	Not Significant
Timeliness	1.335	.259	Not Significant
Accessibility	1.178	.322	Not Significant
Sustainability	.668	.615	Not Significant
Overall	.943	.440	Not Significant

However, to determine the significance of the difference in the perceived level of program implementation of NASA when assessed by respondents when grouped according to educational attainment, the ANOVA was used with post hoc analysis.

As shown in Table 7, there is a significant statistical difference in the perceived level of program implementation as assessed by the respondents when grouped according to educational attainment. The overall F-value is 2.648 while the p-value is .025 with

a post hoc analysis of high school graduates and college graduates. Since some factors are lower than the 0.05 level of significance, then we can reject the null hypothesis and conclude that not all group means are equal. This further means a significant statistical difference in the program implementation of NASA as assessed by the respondents when grouped by educational attainment.

Table 7 Statistical Difference on Perceived Level of Program Implementation by Educational Attainment

EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT			
Factors	F	p-value	Post Hoc Analysis
Disaster Resilience	2.299	.047	High School Graduate & College Graduate
Participation and Project Management	1.921	.093	
Timeliness	2.207	.056	
Accessibility	2.097	.068	
Sustainability	2.428	.037	Elementary Level & College Graduate High School Graduate & College Graduate
Overall	2.648	.025	High School Graduate & College Graduate

Additionally, the ANOVA was used to determine the significance of the difference in the perceived level of program implementation of NASA when assessed by respondents when grouped according to monthly income.

As shown in Table 8, there is no significant difference in the perceived level of program implementation as assessed by the respondents when grouped according to monthly income. Overall, the F-value is .303, while the p-value is .875. In disaster resilience, the F-value is .108, while the p-value is .980. Regarding participation and project management, the F-value is .663, while the p-value is .619. Whereas for the timeliness, the F-value is .161 while the p-value is .958. For accessibility, the F-value is .297, while the p-value is .880. For sustainability, the F-value is .526, while the p-value is .717. All factors are higher than the 0.05 level of significance; thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that the program implementation of NASA is similar as assessed by the respondents when grouped by monthly income.

Table 8 Statistical Difference on Perceived Level of Program Implementation by Monthly Income

MONTHLY INCOME			
Factors	F	p-value	Remarks
Disaster Resilience	.108	.980	Not Significant
Participation and Project Management	.663	.619	Not Significant
Timeliness	.161	.958	Not Significant
Accessibility	.297	.880	Not Significant
Sustainability	.526	.717	Not Significant
Overall	.303	.875	Not Significant

Also, the ANOVA was used to determine the significance of the difference in the perceived level of program implementation of NASA when assessed by respondents when grouped according to occupation.

As shown in Table 9, there is no significant difference in the perceived level of program implementation as assessed by the respondents when grouped according to occupation. Overall, the F-value is .954, while the p-value is .434. In disaster resilience, the F-value is .872, while the p-value is .482. Regarding participation and project management, the F-value is .933, while the p-value is .446. Whereas for the timeliness, the F-value is 1.245 while the p-value is .294. For accessibility, the F-value is .859, while the p-value is .469. For sustainability, the F-value is .696, while the p-value is .595. All factors are higher than the 0.05 level of significance; thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means there is no significant difference in the program implementation of NASA as assessed by the respondents when grouped by occupation.

Table 9 Statistical Difference on Perceived Level of Program Implementation by Occupation

OCCUPATION			
Factors	F	p-value	Remarks
Disaster Resilience	.872	.482	Not Significant
Participation and Project Management	.933	.446	Not Significant
Timeliness	1.245	.294	Not Significant
Accessibility	.859	.469	Not Significant
Sustainability	.696	.595	Not Significant
Overall	.954	.434	Not Significant

In addition, the ANOVA was used to determine the significance of the difference in the perceived level of program implementation of NASA when analyzed as assessed by respondents when grouped according to the number of household members.

As shown in Table 10, there is no significant difference in the perceived level of program implementation as assessed by the respondents when grouped according to the number of household members. Overall, the F-value is .364, while the p-value is .695. In disaster resilience, the F-value is .423, while the p-value is .656. Regarding participation and project management, the F-value is .853, while the p-value is .428. Whereas for the timeliness, the F-value is 1.149 while the p-value is .319. For accessibility, the F-value is .332, while the p-value is .718. For sustainability, the F-value is .462, while the p-value is .631. All factors are higher than the 0.05 level of significance; thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that the program implementation of NASA is similar as assessed by the respondents when grouped by the number of household members.

Table 10 Statistical Difference on Perceived Level of Program Implementation by Number of Household Members

NUMBER OF HOUSEHOLD MEMBERS			
Factors	F	p-value	Remarks
Disaster Resilience	.423	.656	Not Significant
Participation and Project Management	.852	.428	Not Significant
Timeliness	1.149	.319	Not Significant
Accessibility	.332	.718	Not Significant
Sustainability	.462	.631	Not Significant
Overall	.364	.695	Not Significant

The ANOVA was used to determine the significance of the difference in the perceived level of program implementation of NASA when analyzed as assessed by respondents when grouped according to the number of years as beneficiaries.

Table 11 shows no significant difference in the perceived level of program implementation as assessed by the respondents when grouped according to the number of years as beneficiaries. Overall, the F-value is .437, while the p-value is .556. In disaster resilience, the F-value is 1.913, while the p-value is .110. Regarding participation and project management, the F-value is .565, while the p-value is .876. Whereas for the timeliness, the F-value is .165 while the p-value is .766. For accessibility, the F-value is .546, while the p-value is .790. For sustainability, the F-value is .274, while the p-value is .131. All factors are higher than the 0.05 level of significance; thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means there is no significant difference in the program implementation of NASA as assessed by the respondents when grouped by the number of years as beneficiaries.

Table 11 Statistical Difference on Perceived Level of Program Implementation by Number of Years as Beneficiary

NUMBER OF YEARS AS BENEFICIARY			
Factors	F	p-value	Remarks
Disaster Resilience	1.913	.110	Not Significant
Participation and Project Management	.565	.876	Not Significant
Timeliness	.165	.766	Not Significant
Accessibility	.546	.790	Not Significant
Sustainability	.274	.131	Not Significant
Overall	.437	.556	Not Significant

Based on Table 4 to Table 11, regarding the significance of the difference in the perceived level of program implementation of NASA when analyzed by beneficiary-respondent's profile, all indicators except the educational attainment revealed no significant difference. This further implies that the respondents had the same perceptions of the program implementation of NASA regardless of age, sex, marital status, monthly income, occupation, number of household members, and number of years as beneficiaries.

On the other hand, regarding the respondents' educational attainment, some factors, not all group means, are equal. This further means a significant statistical difference in the program implementation of NASA as assessed by the respondents when grouped by educational attainment. This further implies that since most of the respondents belong to the elementary level, NASA has carefully chosen those who have not acquired a higher level of education.

TITLE : NASA-DAVAO ORIENTAL ENHANCEMENT PROGRAM
PROPONENT : RONALD GOMEZ ULGASAN
DURATION : January to December 2023
BUDGETARY REQUIREMENT : P 350,000.00
SOURCE OF FUNDS : Provincial Social Welfare and Development Office
RATIONALE

The Neighborhood Association for Shelter Assistance (NASA) was developed and locally launched by the Provincial Government through the Provincial Social Welfare and Development Office in Davao Oriental as an appropriate reaction to the province's 80% of disaster-prone districts. The resettlement program offers housing aid to displaced squatter families and homeless disaster victims who have little money to rebuild their homes. To teach the beneficiaries of NASA the value of social responsibility in maintaining and preserving the shelter provision project, the local government made a Memorandum of Agreement with them.

The evaluation of projects, however, is crucial in the quest to increase value creation in social housing. The review procedure, however, could be hampered by the project objectives' diversity, volatility, and lack of clarity. Without creating a clear connection with anticipated aims, the evaluation of social housing projects is primarily concerned with product features.

The LGU and other project stakeholders must get involved to enhance and improve the project's serviceability in the aforementioned factors, despite the high manifestation of the success indicators of the implementation of NASA based on disaster resilience, participation, project management, timeliness, accessibility, and sustainability.

D. Objectives

➤ *General*

This enhancement program aims to help NASA beneficiaries learn, improve their knowledge, adjust their attitudes, and enhance their skills in the management and enhancement of NASA management to make it sustainable, thereby improving the well-being of the beneficiaries, men and women alike.

• *Specific*

- ✓ Organize/establish NASA at different sites in the province;
- ✓ Train beneficiaries;
- ✓ Develop and enhance the capacity of the men & women beneficiaries, housing project management; and
- ✓ For NASA beneficiaries to internalize and attain a shared understanding of this housing project.

E. Methodology

- For disaster resilience, NASA must implement measures to prevent or mitigate disaster occurrence. By this, the intervention is to conduct initial evaluations and delineation by LGUs. With the aid of technical and local partners, employing 1:10,000, identify no-build zones, protection regions, and high-risk locations using scaled topographic maps and geohazard maps. Then, evaluate the hazards associated with each, including the associated cost of mitigation measures. Rebuilding on-site versus moving off-site requires different strategies and has various constraints. MGB can then conduct a geohazard identification survey based on the first topographic assessment.
- For participation and project management, NASA has to mobilize the support of different government agencies to provide community facilities and social services on the site. In connection with this, NASA must strengthen stakeholders' linkages in providing facilities and social services.
- Regarding timeliness, NASA must acquire buildable sites by creating and strictly following a timetable. The PSWDO must create timetables after consulting with community members, incorporating anticipated delays and maintaining schedule flexibility, subject to verification of on-site circumstances. The process may move quicker if recipient households can employ builders independently, but this must be accompanied by technical help and control from LGU and PSWDO technical staff.
- For accessibility, NASA members must pay their association loans religiously. In this case, there must be concrete planning and implementation of sanctions and benefits of the loaners by letting them pay in staggered. A term plan option known as staggered payment allows the nominee(s) to receive some of the sum assured as a lump sum and the remainder in monthly or yearly installments.
- For sustainability, NASA has to plan for small projects using its funds and local resources. Thus, the members must increase their assets by drafting Income Generating Projects using their funds and resources.

CHAPTER FOUR CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This chapter describes the conclusions and recommendations drawn from the study's outcomes.

Based on the findings of this study, beneficiary-respondents' profile varies in terms of age, sex, marital status, educational attainment, monthly income, occupation, number of household members, and number of years as beneficiary. The researcher recommends that NASA shall maintain this data profile of the respondents.

Moreover, the perceived level of program implementation of NASA in terms of disaster resilience, participation and project management, timeliness, accessibility, and sustainability are very highly manifested; hence it can be deduced that the implementation of the project has been efficient and effective. Nonetheless, it must be improved to adapt to the demands and hazards of today's socio-economic living standards.

Additionally, the significance of the difference in the perceived level of program implementation of NASA when analyzed by beneficiary-respondent's profile can be surmised that all of the indicators except the educational attainment revealed no significant difference; hence regardless of their differences in their demographic profile, the majority of them have similar responses.

Nevertheless, despite the high level of manifestation of the success indicators of the implementation of NASA based on disaster resilience, participation and project management, timeliness, accessibility, and sustainability, it is still conclusive to say that there is a need for intervention by the LGU and other stakeholders for the project to enhance and improve its serviceability in the aforementioned factors.

The researcher concludes that the very high-level manifestation has been in line with the principles of the National Incident Management System, which states that most incidents start and end locally and typically call for a coordinated effort from local agencies, the private sector, and NGOs.

The results were also consistent with the hierarchical model for value production, which uses attributes to link to outcomes and intended aims as a social housing project evaluation tool. This has demonstrated that, despite being spread out over the project's implementation, the beneficiaries have achieved their objectives successfully.

To implement large-scale solutions and allocate resources effectively, the national government and local government units still need to standardize a clear strategy that outlines the essential coordination and roles of the national government agencies involved in housing responses, such as NASA.

For further planning and implementation of the points of the suggested intervention, the PSWDO, LGU, and NASA shall disseminate the study's findings and proposed intervention.

Future researchers may undertake a similar study in other locations around the province and other localities to explore and compare the instances and scenarios of the NASA implementation to further craft intervention. Furthermore, the researcher would like to endorse this paper as a groundwork for future research to future researchers.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Amole, O. et. al. (2010). Evaluation of Public Housing Programmes in Nigeria: A Theoretical and Conceptual Approach. *The Built & Human Environment Review*, Volume 3. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/228465876_Evaluation_of_Public_Housing_Programmes_in_Nigeria_A_Theoretical_and_Conceptual_Approach
- [2]. Angel, Carol et.al (2015). Assessing the Compliance of Balanced Housing Policy in the Philippines: The Case of Davao City Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/283705540_Assessing_the_Compliance_of_Balanced_Housing_Policy_in_the_Philippines_The_Case_of_Davao_City.
- [3]. Belli, G. (2008). Nonexperimental Quantitative Research. Retrieved from <https://scirp.org/reference/referencespapers.aspx?referenceid=2641699>
- [4]. Bonatto, Fernanda et. al (2011). Evaluation of Social Housing Projects Based on User Perceived Value Hierarchy. Retrieved from http://www.scielo.br/scielo.php?pid=S1678-86212011000100006&script=sci_abstract
- [5]. Department of Social Welfare and Development Office (2011). DSWD 2 Ranks 2nd in the Core Shelter Assistance Program Implementation Nationwide Retrieved from <https://reliefweb.int/report/philippines/dswd-2-ranks-2nd-core-shelter-assistance-program-implementation-nationwide>
- [6]. Fagan, K. et al (2007). Approaches to evaluation of affordable housing initiatives in Australia. National Research Venture 3: Housing affordability for lower income Australians. Australian Housing and Urban Research Institute Sydney Research Centre. Retrieved from https://www.ahuri.edu.au/_data/assets/pdf_file/0022/2695/NRV3_Research_Paper_7.pdf
- [7]. FEMA (2020). Federal Emergency Management Agency. US Department of Homeland Security. Planning Considerations: Disaster Housing. Retrieved from <https://www.fema.gov/sites/default/files/2020-07/planning-considerations-disaster-housing.pdf>
- [8]. Fidler, D. & Sabir, H. (2019). The Cost of Housing Is Tearing Our Society Apart. Retrieved from <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2019/01/why-housing-appreciation-is-killing-housing/>
- [9]. Florida, R., (2017). Anatomy of a NIMBY. Retrieved from <https://www.citylab.com/equity/2017/02/california-land-use-housing-affordability/517320/>
- [10]. Gutman, J. (1982) "A means-end chain model based on consumer categorization processes. *Journal of Marketing*, 46 (2), 60-72.
- [11]. LACP, 2012. Los Angeles City Planning. Los Angeles/Long Beach/ Riverside Regional Catastrophic Planning Grant Program Region Assessment and Gap Analysis Report, 2012. <https://hcidla.lacity.org/assessment-and-gap-analysis-report>.
- [12]. Mamuyac, Christine (2014) Social Preparation Ensures Effective Core Shelter Implementation, National Economic and Development Authority. Retrieved from <http://car.neda.gov.ph/social-preparation-ensures-effective-core-shelter-implementation-2/>
- [13]. McKinsey Global Institute (2014). McKinsey & Company. Tackling the world's affordable housing challenge. Retrieved from <https://www.mckinsey.com/featured-insights/urbanization/tackling-the-worlds-affordable-housing-challenge>
- [14]. New Urban Agenda (2016). Habitat Conference III. Retrieved from <https://habitat3.org/the-new-urban-agenda/>
- [15]. Oudshoorn, A., Forchuk, C., Hall, J. C., & Carrier T. S., (2018). An Evaluation of a Housing First Program for Chronically Homeless Women. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/335255267_An_evaluation_of_a_Housing_First_program_for_chronically_homeless_women
- [16]. Parsons, V.L. (2017) Stratified Sampling. Available at <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118445112.stat05999.pub2>
- [17]. Philippine Development Plan (2017). Accelerating Infrastructure Development. Retrieved from <http://www.hudcc.gov.ph/sites/default/files/styles/large/public/document/PHILIPPINE%20DEVELOPMENT%20PLAN.pdf>
- [18]. UN (2017). United Nations Report. The Core Shelter Housing Project. Retrieved from <https://world-habitat.org/world-habitat-awards/winners-and-finalists/the-core-shelter-housing-project/>
- [19]. UN Habitat (2016). Only 13% of World's Cities have affordable housing – according to new research. UN Habitat for a Better Urban Future. Retrieved from <https://unhabitat.org/only-13-of-worlds-cities-have-affordable-housing-according-to-new-research>
- [20]. Woodruff, R. B., Gardial, S. (1996). Know Your Customer: New Approaches to Understanding Customer Value and Satisfaction. Blackwell Publishing.
- [21]. World Economic Forum (2019). Making Affordable Housing a Reality in Cities. Retrieved from https://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_Making_Affordable_Housing_A_Reality_In_Cities_report.pdf

APPENDICES

Table 2.1 Level of Program Implementation of the NASA in terms of Disaster Resilience

Item	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
The Local Government Unit Shelter Assistance Project is not exposed to natural hazards.	1.10	4.14	High
The shelter can withstand storms, typhoons, and other calamities.	0.95	4.10	High
The NASA implement measures to prevent or mitigate disaster occurrence.	0.91	3.98	High
NASA integrates measures in all phases of site development, from identification, assessment, planning, design, construction, management, and maintenance (estate management).	0.84	4.04	High
The NASA make modifications to the standard core shelter design, accompanied by regular monitoring from PSWDO.	0.99	3.99	High
Overall	0.76	4.05	High

Table 2.2 Level of Program Implementation of the NASA in terms of Participation and Project Management

Item	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
NASA members participate in site selection, planning and development.	0.95	4.29	Very High
NASA members participate in house construction-related activities.	0.87	4.44	Very High
NASA members provided inexperienced labor during construction for their sweat equity, assisting the skilled laborers hired by the LGU.	0.99	4.07	High
NASA changes the life of beneficiaries into a better living after relocating.	0.83	4.28	Very High
NASA conduct livelihood programs specifically targeted for the beneficiaries.	1.03	3.97	High
NASA mobilizes the support of different government agencies to provide community facilities and social services in the site.	0.87	3.93	High
NASA coordinates and agrees on decisions related to relocation, beneficiary selection and housing construction.	0.80	4.23	Very High
NASA beneficiaries integrate and maximize available resources from all participating entities adopting a common term of reference for site planning and development to include the menu of housing options and assistance.	0.95	3.99	High
NASA beneficiaries accomplish are the documentation requirements administered through other government agencies, and local government.	0.89	4.01	High
NASA officers monitor and evaluate the implementation of plans, programs, and projects as well as the operations of the sub-committees.	0.92	4.01	High
Overall	0.73	4.06	High

Table 2.3 Level of Program Implementation of the NASA in terms Timeliness

Item	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
The beneficiaries finish the construction of the houses sooner than the expected time.	0.93	4.00	High
The timeliness of providing housing units is being impeded by the challenge of acquiring buildable sites.	1.03	3.64	High
The construction working requirements are on a deliverable basis without asking for a mobilization advance.	0.93	3.92	High
The beneficiaries moved in on the scheduled time.	0.88	4.03	High
Changes were made in the process of site selection, planning, development, housing design and construction.	0.92	4.10	High
Overall	0.77	3.94	High

Table 2.4 Level of Program Implementation of the NASA in terms of Accessibility

Item	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Basic services are in or near the relocation site.	1.06	4.02	High
Employment and livelihood are accessible in the relocation site.	1.17	3.73	High
Electricity and water connections have reached the site.	0.79	4.53	Very High
NASA beneficiaries have a clear payment terms and conditions.	0.90	4.16	High
NASA members pay their association loans religiously.	1.04	3.71	High
Overall	0.69	3.98	High

Table 2.5 Level of Program Implementation of the NASA in terms of Sustainability

Item	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
The families in the NASA are organized to improve living conditions in the relocation.	0.85	4.34	Very High
The NASA officers assumed on carry-over capacity.	0.88	4.01	High
The NASA treasurer sustains its collections of monthly dues.	0.88	4.04	High
NASA plans for small projects using their funds and local resources.	0.95	3.77	High
NASA members undertake community labor to sustain and improve the relocation site.	0.97	3.91	High
Overall	0.73	4.01	High

SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE ON ASSESSMENT OF NEIGHBORHOOD ASSOCIATION FOR SHELTER ASSISTANCE IMPLEMENTATION IN DAVAO ORIENTAL: BASIS FOR PROGRAM ENHANCEMENT

Dear Sir/Madam:

My name is **RONALD GOMEZ ULGASAN** I conducted a research study entitled “**ASSESSMENT OF NEIGHBORHOOD ASSOCIATION FOR SHELTER ASSISTANCE IMPLEMENTATION IN DAVAO ORIENTAL: BASIS FOR PROGRAM ENHANCEMENT**”. You have been selected to take part in this study because you are the beneficiaries of the LGU Shelter Assistance Project organized into the Neighborhood Association for Shelter Assistance (NASA). Therefore, I kindly request you to spare some of your valuable time and respond to these questions. Note that all responses including your identity will be treated with most confidentiality and shall be exclusively for purpose of this research study.

Thank you.

RONALD GOMEZ ULGASAN
Researcher

Noted By:

MINDA B. BRIGOLI, DRD
Thesis Adviser

➤ *Socio- Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents*

1. Age Bracket

- 30 years old and below 51 - 60
 31 - 40 61 - 70
 41 – 50 above 70 years old

2. Sex

- Male
 Female

3. Marital Status

- Single Separated
 Married Live-in
 Widow/Widower

- 4. Educational Attainment
 - Elementary Level High School Graduate
 - Elementary Graduate College Level
 - High School Level College Graduate

- 5. Monthly Income
 - 5,000 below 20,001 - 25,000
 - 5,001 – 10,000 25,000 above
 - 10,001 – 15,000.00
 - 15,001 – 20,000

- 6. Occupation
 - Fishing Private/Public Employee
 - Farming Others Please Specify _____
 - Carpentry

- 7. How many people live in your household including yourself?
 - 1-5 16-20
 - 6-10 21-25
 - 11-15 26 above

- 8. How long have been a beneficiary of NASA?
 - Below 5 years 16 – 20 years
 - 6-10 years 21 years above
 - 11-15 years

11. PERCEIVED LEVEL OF PROGRAM IMPLEMENTATION OF NEIGHBORHOOD ASSOCIATION FOR SHELTER ASSISTANCE (NASA)

Direction: Honestly and sincerely respond to each item with the scale that best represents a true assessment of yourself. Each scale is interpreted below. Check the box of your response. *(Tubaga ang matag aytem nga matinud-anon ug sinsero gamit ang sukdanan nga nagrepresentar sa usa ka tinuod nga pagsusi sa imong kaugalingon. Ang matag sukod gihubad sa ubos. E-tsekang kahon sa imong tubag.)*

➤ *Rating Scale and Interpretation:*

Scale	Interpretation
5	The measure of the variable statement is always true
4	The measure of the variable statement is often true
3	The measure of the variable statement is sometimes true
2	The measure of the variable statement is seldom true
1	The measure of the variable statement is almost never true

ASSESSMENT OF NEIGHBORHOOD ASSOCIATION FOR SHELTER ASSISTANCE IMPLEMENTATION IN DAVAO ORIENTAL: BASIS FOR PROGRAM ENHANCEMENT						
A. DISASTER RESILIENCE						
<i>To what extent does Neighborhood Association for Shelter Assistance is evident in terms of disaster resilience?</i>		1	2	3	4	5
1	The Local Government Unit Shelter Assistance Project is not exposed to natural hazards. <i>(Ang proyekto nga pabalay sa local nga panggamhanan kon LGU –SAP nahilayo sa mga natural na peligro.)</i>					
2	The shelter can withstand storms, typhoons, and other calamities. <i>(Ang pabalay masugakod sa mga unos, bagyo ug uban pang kalamidad.)</i>					
3	The NASA implement measures to prevent or mitigate disaster occurrence. <i>(Ang NASA nagpatuman ug mga lakang aron mapugngan o maminusan ang panghitabo sa katalagman.)</i>					

4	NASA integrates measures in all phases of site development, from identification, assessment, planning, design, construction, management, and maintenance (estate management). <i>(Ghiusa sa NASA ang mga lakang sa tanan nga mga hugna sa pag-uswag sa site, gikan sa pag-ila, pagsusi, pagplano, disenyo, pagtukod, pagdumala, ug pagmentinar (pagdumala sa yuta).</i>					
5	The NASA make modifications to the standard core shelter design, accompanied by regular monitoring from PSWDO. <i>(Ang NASA naghimo og mga kausaban sa standard core shelter design, inubanan sa regular nga monitoring gikan sa PSWDO).</i>					
B. PARTICIPATION AND PROJECT MANAGEMENT						
<i>To what extent does the Neighborhood Association for Shelter Assistance is evident in community participation?</i>		1	2	3	4	5
1	NASA members participate in site selection, planning and development. <i>(Ang mga miyembro sa NASA miapil sa pagpili sa luna, pagplano ug pagpalambo.)</i>					
2	NASA members participate in house construction-related activities. <i>(Ang mg miyembro sa NASA miapil sa mga kalihokan nga may kalabotan sa pagtukod sa balay.)</i>					
3	NASA members provided inexperienced labor during construction for their sweat equity, assisting the skilled laborers hired by the LGU. <i>(Ang mga miyembro sa NASA naghatag ug inexperienced labor atoll sa construction para sa ilang sweat equity, pagtabang sa mga skilled laborers nga gisuhol sa local nga panggamhanan kon LGU.)</i>					
4	NASA changes the life of beneficiaries into a better living after relocating. <i>(Gibag-o sa NASA ang kinabuhi sa mga benepisyaryo ngadto sa mas maayong panginabuhi pagkahuman sa pagbalhin.)</i>					
5	NASA conduct livelihood programs specifically targeted for the beneficiaries. <i>(Ang NASA nagpahigayon ug panginabuhian na programa nga espesipikong nagtumong alang sa mga benepisyaryo.)</i>					
6	NASA mobilizes the support of different government agencies to provide community facilities and social services in the site. <i>(Gipalihok sa NASA ang suporta sa lain laing mga ahensya sa gobyerno aron mahatagan ang mga pasilidad sa komunidad ug serbisyo sosyal sa site.)</i>					
7	NASA coordinates and agrees on decisions related to relocation, beneficiary selection and housing construction. <i>(Ang NASA nakig-koordinar ug nagkauyon sa mga desisyon nga may kalabotan sa relokasyon, pagpili sa benepisyaryo ug pagtukod og balay.)</i>					
8	NASA beneficiaries integrate and maximize available resources from all participating entities adopting a common term of reference for site planning and development to include the menu of housing options and assistance.					

	<i>(Ang mga benepisyaryo sa NASA naghiusa ug nagpadako sa mga kapanguhaan gikan sa tanan nnga nag-apil nga mga entidad nga nagsagop sa us aka sagad nga termino sa pakisayran alang sa pagplano ug –uswag sa site aron maapil ang menu sa mga kapilian sa balay ug tabang.)</i>					
9	NASA beneficiaries accomplish the documentation requirements administered through other government agencies, and the local government. <i>(Natuman sa NASA ang mga kinahanglanon sa dokumentasyon nga gidumala pinaagi sa ubang mga ahensya sa gobyerno, ug local nga panggamhanan.)</i>					
10	NASA officers monitor and evaluate the implementation of plans, programs, and projects as well as the operations of the sub-committee. <i>(Ang mga opisyal sa NASA nagmonitor ug nag evaluate sa pagpatuman sa mga plano, program, ug proyekto ingon man ang mga operasyon sa mga sub-komite.)</i>					

C. TIMELINESS

<i>To what extent does the Neighborhood Association for Shelter Assistance is evident?</i>		1	2	3	4	5
1	The beneficiaries finish the construction of the houses sooner that the expected time. <i>(Ang mga benepisyaryo makahuman sa pagtukod sa mga balay nga mas sayo kaysa gipaabot nga oras.)</i>					
2	The timeliness of providing housing units is being impeded by the challenge of acquiring buildable sites. <i>(Ang tukma sa panahon sa paghatag og mga yunit sa pabalay gibabagan sa hagit sa pag-angkon sa mga dapit nga matukod.)</i>					
3	The construction working requirements are on a deliverable basis without asking for a mobilization advance.) <i>(Ang mga kinahanglanon sa pagtrabaho sa konstruksyon mahatag diha nga dili mangayo ug mobilization advance.)</i>					
4	The beneficiaries moved on the scheduled time. <i>(Ang mga beneficiary mibalhin sa gitakdang oras.)</i>					
5	Changes were made in the process of site selection, planning, development, housing design and construction. <i>(Ang mga pagbag-o gihimo sa proseso sa pagoili sa site, pagplano, pag-uswag, disenyo sa pabalay ug pagtukod niini.)</i>					

D. ACCESSIBILITY

<i>To what extent does the Neighborhood Association for Shelter Assistance is evident in terms of accessibility?</i>		1	2	3	4	5
1	Basic services are in or near the relocation site. <i>(Ang mga batakang serbisyo anaa sa duol sa relocation site)</i>					
2	Employment and livelihood are accessible in the relocation site. <i>(Ang mga pagpanarbaho ug panginabuhian anaa sa relocation site.)</i>					
3	Electricity and water connections have reached the site. <i>(Ang mga koneksyon sa kuryente ug tubig nakaabot sa site.)</i>					

4	NASA beneficiaries have a clear payment terms and conditions. <i>(Ang mga benepisyaryo sa NASA adunay klaro nga termino ug kondisyon sa pagbayad.)</i>					
5	NASA members pay their association loans religiously. <i>(Ang mga miyembro sa NASA relihiyoso nga nagbayad sa ilang mga utang sa asosasyon.)</i>					
E. SUSTAINABILITY						
<i>To what extent does the Neighborhood Association for Shelter Assistance is evident in terms of Sustainability?</i>		1	2	3	4	5
1	To what extent does the Neighborhood Association for Shelter Assistance is evident in terms of Sustainability? <i>(Ang mga pamilya sa NASA giorganisar aron mapaayo ang kahintang sa pagpuyo sa lugar nga reloaksyon.)</i>					
2	The NASA officers assumed on carry-over capacity. <i>(Ang mga opisyal sa NASA nagsalig sa kapasidad sa pagdala.)</i>					
3	The NASA treasurer sustains its collections of monthly dues. <i>(Ang treasurer sa NASA nag sustenir sa mga koleksyon niini sa binuwan nga bayronon.)</i>					
4	NASA plans for small projects using their funds ang local resources. <i>(Nagplano ang NASA alang sa gagmay nga mga proyekto gamit ang ilang mga pondo ug local nga kahinguhaan.)</i>					
5	NASA members undertake community labor to sustain and improve the relocation site. <i>(Ang mga miyembro sa NASA nagpahigayon ug community labor aron mapadayon ug mapaayo ang relocation site.)</i>					

-END OF THE SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE -